

POSITION KHIVA AS A TOURISM DESTINATION RELATED
PROMOTION AND MARKETING

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Abstract. In this article, the processes related to increasing the tourism potential, stabilizing the tourism sector along with the development of the country's economic sectors, ensuring the stability of the tourism potential of the city of Khiva, and the sale of tourism products are covered by the author.

Key words: Khiva city, tourism, tourism, sustainable tourism, tourism facilities.

Introduction. Uzbekistan has great potential for an expanded tourism industry. As one of the focus areas for reform and economic expansion, tourism in the country has increase fivefold in over the last three years. While about 1 million tourists visited Uzbekistan in 2016, the figure rose to 2.7 million in 2017, and more than 5.3 million in 2018. The number of foreign tourists is expected to rise to 7 million by 2025, and the annual foreign currency earnings from foreign visitors will reach as much as \$2 billion.i However, Uzbekistan's tourism sector still faces challenges. These include poor transportation and payment systems, the shortage of appropriate hotels, medical services, language assistance, and information for tourists. Uzbekistan can enhance its tourism potential by strengthening its cooperation with other countries and international organizations. Additionally, Uzbekistan should explore its cultural and natural attractions, and invest in advertising to raise awareness about these sites. To properly utilize its tourism

resources, Uzbekistan also needs to improve infrastructure construction, as well as foster entrepreneurship and other private-sector engagement to realize the country's tourism potential.

Literature review. Tourism is one of the sectors Uzbekistan has sought to reform and revitalize since 2016. Its reform process aims to create jobs and new business opportunities; further the diversification and accelerated development of regions; increase incomes and living standards and quality of life, boost foreign-exchange earnings; and improve Uzbekistan's overall image and investment. Uzbekistan held its first International Investment Forum on November 19-21, 2018 to expand international engagement in the sector and disseminate information about the country's tourism potential.

Although Uzbekistan has made substantial efforts and launched numerous reforms to expand and improve its tourism industry as part of its program of economic growth, further actions are needed. The Uzbek government has addressed shortcomings inconveniences still connected with border procedures, transportation, and guest accommodations. Still, some support facilities and services require action by the government or private sector, especially given the role they play in attracting tourists or encouraging them to become repeat visitors. The Uzbekistan International Visitor Economy Survey 2014 by the World Tourism Organization, showed respondents frequently noted inconveniences. These included problems with the payments system (especially lack of access to cash via ATM), Internet problems (little access to Wi-Fi and slow speed), limited English translation of signage and tourist information at tourist attractions, and electricity outages.^{xxvi} Furthermore, as noted in an interview with a local tour guide conducted by Silk Road New Observation News Agency, concerns about the wholesomeness of food products, the availability and quality of medical services, and the lack of clean, modern public restrooms are frequently cited.^{xxvii} Because of the often poor medical services in outlying areas, tourists who fall ill in these

locales need to be moved swiftly to Tashkent's international hospital. At the same time, the practice whereby a tour group will wait for the patient to recover and then depart the country all together can produce large costs and additional concerns for fellow tourists and their travel agency as they wait for the patient's treatment to end.

Data and methodology. Tourism is a part of the social sphere and performs a number of functions, such as creating conditions for recreation, providing health care, serving the consumption process, and forming the general information and cultural level of the population. The development dynamics of the national tourism balance can be considered as one of the indicators of prosperity and development of the country's economy. Tourism, one of the most profitable types of business in the world, can also bring great benefits to tourist regions around the world. Some experts highly assess the country's tourism potential.

Result. Special attention was paid to the problems of establishing merchant advertising companies. Therefore, in the first stage of evolution (1900-1940s), marketing was related to sales and was called "sales marketing". Marketing in tourism is a part of objective reality, an integral part of the life of this industry. Its necessity and efficiency depends on the current level of development of market relations. The use of the concept of marketing in the field of tourism provides the following opportunities:

establishing bilateral relations between sellers and buyers of tourist products through market research and promotion;

setting the parameters of production of tourism products depending on the existing and potential demand and purchasing power of consumers;

as the main goal of tourism is to meet the needs of customers.

The main directions of marketing activities in the field of tourism:

1) determining the quality and price parameters of demand, characteristics and priorities in relation to potential and real consumers;

- 2) formation of the scope of provided services and additional services;
- 3) to assess and ensure the necessary level of the quality of services provided;
- 4) services for selection and decision-making according to the required amount and order of service;
- 5) selection and decision-making on logistics issues of service provision;
- 6) defining characteristics and priorities for employees who provide basic, additional and related services in the field of tourism;
- 7) determination of service prices, terms and forms of payment, methods of price regulation;
- 8) organization of advertising and sales of tourist products.

A distinctive feature of marketing in tourism is that the demand for services is constantly growing, but depends to some extent on changes in the economic situation. Reliable information about consumers is of great importance in marketing analysis. Tourist seasonal factors have a specific effect on the development of tourism, which requires diversification of tourist services, active marketing during the tourist season. Since the tourist product consists of complex material and organizational parts, it is necessary to coordinate the marketing of all companies involved in the production of the tourism product.

Thus, in the tourist market, the needs for recreation and recreation turn into the needs to change the environment, such needs into the desire to move, and these desires, taking into account the possibilities, into the demand for specific products (destination) in the tourist market goes; The exchange between the producer and the buyer of the tourist product is carried out in the form of trade (making a tourist trip). It follows from this that marketing allows the tourist enterprise (the entire economy) to satisfy the constantly changing requirements (needs) of many consumers. directs. In other words, tourism marketing is a management philosophy (the direction of its implementation) in which solving the problems of consumers

by effectively meeting their needs leads to the success of the organization, which in turn contributes to society. also benefits.

Marketing in tourism in general is not fundamentally different from any important marketing rules. Therefore, all the main principles of modern marketing can be very well applied in the field of tourism. But it should be taken into account that the tourism business has its own characteristics. We will analyze them in more detail. Tourism marketing deals with the sale of goods and services. According to experts, is the share of services in each tourist enterprise just high, or how do goods make up everything in it? There will be questions like. The concept of marketing has such a specific content for traditional types of commercial activities that have a certain result of work. Tourism product in tourism activity is a product of labor. Under this term, it is customary to understand any service provided to tourists (household, hotel, transport, attractions, etc.). A tourism product can also be understood as a system of goods and services that make up a trip together.

Conclusion. According to the results of many marketing researches in the field of tourism, you can come to the conclusion that in order to attract a potential tourist, the first place is a live invitation. This, in turn, can be divided into recreation, sports, health care. Taking into account all these factors, it is necessary to implement attractive tours with the offer of a number of additional services that will maximally satisfy one or another target segment. For example, live calling (through live advertising) plays a very important role for young people. This is the activity of young tourists and their need for cheap services.

For middle-aged people or businessmen, quality service, availability of cultural programs, certain elitism, prestige are more important. Services such as cultural and health care are important for the elderly. It is also necessary to take into account the psychological motivation of people, who want to visit new places, get to know people's way of life, and just relax. In the third place is cultural motivation, that is, interest in art. Tourism marketing does not differ from other

forms of economic activity in its important features. Therefore, all existing features of modern marketing can be fully applied in tourism. At the same time, there is a feature that distinguishes tourism not only from trade in products, but also from other forms of trade in services. Here, both trade and service take place as products (according to experts, services make up 75% of tourism, products 25%), and tourism service and product consumption are important in their production. becomes important.

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